

Sustainable Development Adaptation and Commitment to Work of Teachers

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Abstract. The study intended to determine the extent of sustainable development adaptation employed as the determinant of the commitment to work of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City Division. The findings revealed that sustainable development adaptation in terms of environmental awareness, competencies for the knowledge economy, and human and social capital was always manifested. Teachers have effectively integrated environmental awareness into the curriculum. This was manifested by how they improved their living standards and addressed the issues relevant to humanity. In return, the learners were able to equip themselves with processes for protecting the coming generations since they rated very extensively for the majority of the indicators. However, some items in competencies for the knowledge economy, such as getting only accurate information regarding the disaster, are extensive. Education is an important factor in making the communities well-informed about the measures that would help address a sustainable environment. However, the commitment to work in terms of affective, continuance, and normative commitment was very extensive, such as consistently striving to meet targets and objectives. Sustainable development adaptation and commitment to work showed a significant relationship. Lastly, indicators of sustainable development adaptation competencies for knowledge economy and human and social capital significantly influence the commitment to the work of teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. Sustainable Development 2. Adaptation 3. Commitment 4. Work of Teachers

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1. Introduction

The strong economic growth experienced over the last century has been accompanied by gains in material welfare worldwide. World GDP is projected to expand by 75 percent between 1995 and 2020, bringing increased pressures on environmental and social resources. Governments pursuing sustainable development face the challenge of discerning how best to balance the challenges and opportunities of growth and to decouple economic growth from environmental pressures. Given the global nature of many of the most pressing development challenges, such as climate change, it is imperative that countries build strong coalitions to address issues of common concern and that they adapt institutions and decision-making processes to ever-increasing globalization. Today's curriculum integrates sustainability in many aspects.

Teachers are encouraged to create class activities that reflect students' development in valuing the environment while developing essential life skills necessary in work when they become adults. As a result, students become more participative in environmental-related activities that aim to conserve natural resources. In this aspect, schools become effective vehicles for making sustainability a way of life for the students. Sustainable development takes form when achieving ecological balance becomes the ultimate goal of basic government institutions while continuing to develop the environment for the benefit of the people. Therefore, it is essential that teacher education not only encompasses sustainability concepts but also offers holistic and interdisciplinary teaching methods on the topic (Yemini et al., 2019; Saperstein, 2020). Diverse regional, cultural, economic, and political factors shape the incorporation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into teacher education, necessitating tailored approaches (Leicht et al., 2018). Recognizing these differences can enhance the effectiveness of programs, foster collaboration, and build a global network of educators ready to address local sustainability issues (Caniglia et al., 2018; Dür Keller, 2018). Teachers in Malaysia find it extremely challenging to integrate sustainable development into their curricula. Problems stem mostly from a need for more specialized training and resources, which make it difficult for teachers to incorporate these ideas into their instruction. Urban-rural educational infrastructure gaps exacerbate these problems, with less established schools frequently needing more resources and assistance teaching sustainability (Yusof Abdul Rahman, 2019). Despite these obstacles, continuous attempts are being made to enhance the incorporation of sustainable development within Malaysian education. Professional development programs and cooperative initiatives are being developed to improve teachers' sustainability-related skills and resources

(Ismail et al., 2019). These programs should help educators feel more supported and committed to sustainability. As these initiatives pick up steam, they could close current gaps and foster a more cohesive approach to sustainability in the Malaysian educational system. US teaching professionals face several obstacles to addressing sustainable development in the classroom. One of the main problems is the inconsistent way sustainability is incorporated into curricula in various states and school districts. Teachers frequently encounter challenges such as a shortage of resources for sustainable teaching and opportunities for professional development. These elements influence the adoption of sustainable practices in the classroom at different degrees of commitment (Simmons et al., 2019). Despite these obstacles, initiatives are in motion to improve education on sustainability. Several projects are being launched to fill these voids, including integrating sustainability requirements into curriculum frameworks and creating specialist training courses for teachers (Klein et al., 2019). With the help of these initiatives, educators hope to equip themselves and their students better to include sustainability in their lessons. With more of these programs underway, there's a chance that sustainability education will become more unified and all-encompassing nationwide. The dedication of teachers to their responsibilities and adaptation provides major obstacles to Nigeria's sustainable development. According to Ilgaz et al. (2019), teachers in Nigeria are essential to attaining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), but their capacity to do so is frequently hampered by a lack of funding, poor training, and low morale. The study emphasizes the necessity of investing significantly in teachers' professional development and working circumstances if they are completely committed to sustainable development. Grund et al. (2019) argue that structural problems, including low pay and a lack of assistance from educational authorities, also impact

teachers' commitment to sustainable development. The study emphasizes the significance of changing policies to improve working conditions for teachers and offer continuing professional development. By tackling these issues, Nigeria will be in a better position to leverage the potential of its teachers to promote sustainable development and meet long-term social and educational objectives. Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is highly relevant to contemporary development challenges, yet its implementation remains a significant concern in the Philippines. The primary challenge is determining how to effectively integrate ESD to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that nations globally are committed to. ESD is considered crucial for preparing for the future, providing quality education, and facilitating the transition to environmentally sustainable societies and economies (UNESCO, 2018). At the tertiary level, ESD is approached through various strategies, adapting university education to incorporate sustainability concepts and address customization needs effectively. The country's dedication to education has recently been strengthened by introducing the K to 12 programs, a significant reform in Philippine primary education aimed at systematically preparing the youth to face the challenges of globalization and sustainable development. Following this initiative, efforts have advanced to higher education levels, where considerable progress has been made. Secondary education institutions are now actively involved in dynamic international collaborations to develop and implement innovative teaching practices that promote and enhance socio-cultural and environmental awareness (UNESCO 2018). In the Philippines, teachers' poor work commitment is evident in their low attendance at parent-teacher conferences, delayed submission of reports like class nutritional status, and failure to distribute students' report cards on the scheduled date. Some teachers do not home visit students at the risk

of dropping out. School heads are alarmed by these teachers' negligence, which might cause future problems for the stakeholders (Cacayan, 2019). In the local setting, at the time of the study, the Schools Division Superintendent of Digos City Division urged school heads during the Management Committee meeting to immediately address the issue of teacher's delayed submission of the school reports as some teachers are not able to accomplish on time school reports on reading inventory, monthly student's attendance report, and minutes of the conducted home-room meetings. This study was valuable to various stakeholders, including the Department of Education, teachers, and students. For Department of Education officials, the research findings are expected to assist school administrators in designing effective courses and workshops, thereby aiding students and educators in developing robust lesson plans and sound academic policies. Through the study's findings, teachers may gain insights into how they can support their colleagues' professional growth and development. Students stand to benefit from a deeper understanding of the teaching-learning strategies employed by their educators. Additionally, the results of this study could serve as a benchmark for future researchers, informing curriculum development and future planning by providing a reference point for evaluating the effectiveness of educational practices and policies. The importance of commitment to teachers' work cannot be overemphasized, much more so for teachers' sustainable development adaptation. In this context, the researcher would like to study the two variables. The realization of this study, therefore, contributed to new knowledge and the existing literature on each of the topics covered in this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

This section examines the relationship between sustainable development adaptation and teacher commitment, focusing on environmental awareness, competencies for the knowledge economy,

and social capital.

1.1.1. Sustainable Development Adaptation—Education is essential for promoting sustainable development by fostering environmental awareness and social responsibility (Boevende Pauw, 2019). Integrating sustainable development principles into education enhances understanding of environmental issues and encourages proactive behavior (Moustairas et al., 2022). Teachers, as role models, play a significant role in shaping environmentally conscious behaviors in students (Yu et al., 2021).

1.1.2. Competencies for the Knowledge Economy—Teachers need skills in critical thinking, problem-solving, and technology integration to prepare students for the future workforce (Schunk Greene, 2019). Ongoing professional development ensures teachers stay updated with the latest tools and techniques, improving student outcomes (Darling-Hammond, 2019). Collaborative teaching approaches and fostering a growth mindset are also crucial for adapting to the knowledge economy (Hargreaves Fullan, 2019; Zhao, 2019).

1.1.3. Social Capital—Social and human capital are vital in enhancing education systems and teacher performance. Professional development and strong social networks foster collaboration and support, creating sustainable learning environments (Becker, 2019; Putnam, 2019). Leadership plays a key role in utilizing these resources to drive educational progress (Leithwood Sun, 2019).

1.1.4. Commitment to Work—Teacher commitment is influenced by job resources, leadership, and school culture. Supportive work environments, transformational leadership, and shared values boost teacher engagement and commitment (Bakker Demerouti, 2019; Leithwood Sun, 2019; Schein, 2019).

1.1.5. Types of Commitment—Affective Commitment: Emotional attachment to the organization, leading to higher job satisfaction and performance (Rayo, 2022; Amin et al., 2018).

Continuance Commitment: Staying with the organization due to the perceived costs of leaving, such as loss of benefits or stability (Baoc-Daguisonan, 2018). Normative Commitment: A sense of moral obligation to remain with the organization, driven by ethical considerations (Al Jabri Ghazzawi, 2019).

1.2. Theoretical Lens—This study was aligned with the pronouncement of Cherkowski (2004), which stated that educators with a high sense of sustainable development adaptation are most likely to be highly dedicated and committed to their functions. This means that the more knowledgeable educators are on the pressing issues that matter, such as concerns related to the social economy or inclusive education, the more enthusiasm they project in letting the students get to know the societal issues that have a direct and indirect bearing on their being so they can help prepare the students to acquire essential life skills necessary for the challenges in work and life. This study is also supported by the pronouncement of Hartshorn (2009), who stated that the sustainable development adaptation of teachers allows them to be more committed to their work. Teachers with a great understanding of how society functions double their time in making students learn how to navigate the modern world aside from teaching the day's competency. It takes overwhelming commitment from teachers to educate the children and make them understand what society is all about and how rapid societal change can be. This study is also anchored on Mitchell and Sackney's (2009) pronouncement that sustainable learning communities and teaching commitment are essential. This can nourish and sustain passion as educators are increasingly challenged to adapt and shift their practices and mindsets in the rapidly changing educational landscape. Sustaining vibrant learning communities requires more than teachers' commitment to remain with the organization; it requires a commitment to continued growth and learning shared with colleagues.

Sustainable education is broadly recognized as an educational approach that incorporates principles of sustainable development. It aims to cultivate individuals who are aware of sustainability issues and possess critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Rooted in Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), this approach relies on activity-based and experiential teaching methods. However, ongoing debate remains about what enhances learning and how different pedagogical approaches impact students. Evans and Ferreira (2020) argue for integrating ESD into teacher education, highlighting the importance of linking pedagogy with curriculum. Sterling (2012) asserts that sustainable development (SD) necessitates adaptive, participatory, and technology-driven processes, significantly shaping students' mindsets. Known as sustainability pedagogies (Cotton Winter, 2010; Sterling et al., 2012), these practices extend beyond traditional content delivery to foster deep learning, transforming students' perspectives, values, and understanding of the world. Mckeown (2014) emphasizes the importance of ESD pedagogical approaches in preparing students for future sustainability challenges like climate change and social inequity. Traditional lecture-based methods are criticized for failing to provide a comprehensive grasp of sustainability, whereas interactive techniques such as role-play, simulations, and case studies are seen as more effective for building resilience and motivation for sustainable practices (Winter, 2010; Sterling, 2012). Despite the promise of innovative methods, Westwood (2008) notes that teaching ESD requires a nuanced approach, considering developmental, social, and contextual factors, and should be guided by proven research. The concept of sustainability pedagogies encompasses more than just teaching for sustainability; it involves intricate interactions between teachers and students (Loughran, 2013; Wink, 2010). Blake, Sterling, and Goodson (2013) explored that transformative learning seeks to instigate profound changes in learners' capabilities, beliefs, behaviors, and relationships, fostering personal and social transformation (Mezirow, 2009). Sterling (2011) describes this as essential higher-order learning for achieving transformative educational objectives. Christie et al. (2013) highlight that effective sustainability education involves dynamic teaching strategies, concept-based learning, and adequate resources to support ESD initiatives. Despite recognizing the role of higher education in promoting innovative learning (Setter, 2017), modernist principles have been inconsistently applied to sustainability education programs (Ceulemans et al., 2017). Implementing sustainable teaching methods presents challenges and opportunities, such as limited program duration and preparation time, as noted by Aleixandre and Gayoso (1996) and Figueroa (2012). This study aligns with Alam et al. (2020) Work Commitment Theory, a pertinent theoretical model for understanding work-related motivation. It suggests that work commitment stems from the perceived fulfillment of three psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Work Commitment Theory provides a valuable framework for exploring the psychological needs and personal, professional, and environmental factors influencing teacher motivation. Self-efficacy theory, proposed by Albert Bandura, also plays a crucial role, positing that individuals' beliefs in their capabilities to perform specific tasks significantly impact their behavior, motivation, and achievements. According to Bandura (1977), as cited by P. Kumari, Wang, Saahil (2018), self-efficacy beliefs are central to determining whether individuals initiate actions, the effort they exert, and their perseverance when facing obstacles. These beliefs are domain-specific, meaning self-efficacy in one area does not necessarily transfer to another. Competence in a task is essential for professional commitment (Sahakyan et al., 2018), particularly for teachers. A committed teacher must have a degree of

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study

autonomy to employ innovative teaching methods and the competency to execute these methods effectively while considering the nature and context of the students (Flores-Mejorado Reed, 2019). Recent research (Scales et al., 2020) highlights that motivation is a crucial factor influencing both student performance and teacher effectiveness, with a significant correlation between the motivation of both groups. Frenzel et al. (2019) found that teachers' characteristics notably impact student performance, with external motivational factors like teacher remuneration affecting students indirectly. Thus, a motivated teacher can enhance student performance, and it becomes easier to motivate students when the teacher is also motivated (Kalyar et al., 2018). The role of self-efficacy in this context includes various sources of self-efficacy information—mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, social persuasion, and physiological states—that shape individuals' beliefs in their capabilities. For example, success in a task can boost self-efficacy, whereas failure may decrease it unless attributed to external factors. Emerging from this perspective is the three-dimensional model of teacher self-efficacy, designed to address the domain-specific nature of self-efficacy while avoiding the limitations of overly detailed operationalization. This multidimensional model reflects an intermediate domain-specific level, ranging from general confidence in one's professional role to highly task-

specific capability beliefs. In this model, teacher self-efficacy encompasses three domains: self-efficacy for classroom management, reflecting teachers' ability to maintain order; self-efficacy for instructional strategies, referring to their capability to employ diverse teaching methods; and self-efficacy for student engagement, indicating their ability to build relationships with students and foster their motivation and engagement (Perera et al., 2019). Self-efficacy in teachers pertains to their belief in their capacity to perform teaching-related tasks effectively, including lesson planning, classroom management, student assessment, and adapting teaching methods to meet students' diverse needs. In the context of work commitment, self-efficacy significantly influences teachers' dedication to their profession. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to exhibit strong work commitment, as they feel confident in their ability to positively impact student learning and well-being. Teachers tend to persevere through challenges, viewing them as growth opportunities rather than insurmountable obstacles. Self-efficacy contributes to teachers' job satisfaction, motivation, and professional commitment. Bandura (1986) emphasizes the importance of self-regulatory mechanisms—such as goal-setting, progress monitoring, and adaptive strategies—in shaping self-efficacy and work-related outcomes.

The conceptual paradigm is shown in Figure 1. The independent variable of this study is the Sustainable Adaptation of Teachers adopted from the Social Dimension of Education by Mathiasson et al., 2022. The indicator of the independent variable is Environmental Awareness, which refers to the educator's knowledge of environmental conservation practices. The dependent variable of this study is the Commitment to the Work of Teachers, which was taken from Allen and Meyer's Model of Organizational Commitment (Allen and Meyer in the survey of Kuhal et al., (2020). The indicators of the dependent variable are as follows: Af-

fective Commitment, which is the educator's emotional attachment to the organization; Normative Commitment, which is the generalized value of loyalty of the educator to the organization. Continuance Commitment is when an employee remains with a particular organization because there are costs to leaving that outweigh the benefits of taking a new job in a different organization.

1.3. Statement of the Problem—This study aimed to discover the significant relationship between sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

- (1) What is the extent of the sustainable development adaptation of educators in terms of:
 - (1) environmental awareness;
 - (2) competencies for the knowledge economy;
 - (3) human/social capital and economic growth, and
 - (4) inclusive education
- (2) What is the level of commitment to work of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) affective commitment;
 - (2) normative commitment; and
 - (3) continuance commitment.
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers?
- (4) What domains of sustainable development adaptation significantly influence the commitment to the work of teachers?

1.4. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance: H01. There is no significant relationship between sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers. H02. No domain of sustainable development adaptation significantly influences the commitment to the work of teachers. The following terms were used for the convenience of this study. Sustainable Development Adaptation. In this study, the

term refers to teachers' practices in producing students for global citizens who want a sustainable future. This includes teachers' teaching practices on environmental awareness, competencies for the knowledge economy, human/social capital, economic growth, and inclusive education. Commitment to Work of Teachers. In this study, the term refers to the teacher's affective, normative, and continuance commitment.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will discuss the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This includes selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and outlining the data analysis process.

The researcher used artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading demonstrates a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. The study aimed to determine the impact of sustainable development adaptation on the commitment to work of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City Division.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing a correlational technique. A substantial proportion of quantitative educational research is non-experimental because many important variables of interest are not manipulable. Because non-experimental research is an important methodology employed by many researchers, it is important to use a classification system of non-experimental methods that are highly descriptive of what we do and allow us to communicate effectively in an interdisciplinary research environment. According to Dawson (2019), quantitative research methodologies are meant to create numeric statistics by using survey research to gather data. Qualitative research methodologies examine individuals' behaviors, opinions, and experiences through examination methods. Diverse numerical data were gathered using various techniques in this kind of research, and the data were then statistically processed to aggregate, compare, or demonstrate correlations between the data. Experiments, organized observations, and surveys are examples of quantitative research methodologies.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were one hundred elementary school teachers of Digos Oriental District, Digos City Division, who were randomly selected. The respondents are permanent elementary teachers in the service for three years. A sample size of one hundred was obtained using the fishbowl technique. In this technique, the researcher would randomly pick teachers' names from the fishbowl. These teachers were considered the study respondents.

2.3. Research Instrument—The researcher utilized adapted questionnaires from Wegner's studies (2021), which were modified to suit the present study's concept, place, situation, and ideas. The draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations. The final copy of the research survey questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts for approval. The final revision incorporated all the corrections, comments, and suggestions the experts gave before distribution and administration. Some expert validators presented and evaluated the draft of the questionnaire. They were given a standard evaluation tool to rate, comment on, and suggest improvements and development of the questionnaire. The validation results, together with the draft of the research instrument, were submitted to the research adviser for comments and suggestions. The ambiguous items were deleted, and the weak items were strengthened and improved. After correction and refinement, the research instrument was returned to the researcher for finalization. The pilot testing was conducted in Digos Occidental District, and the respondents were not included in the research survey. It was purposely conducted to establish the reliability and validity of the test instrument. The questionnaire was designed and modified to suit the respondents' needs. This study used a self-constructed questionnaire designed to gather information concerning the impact of sustainable development adaptation on teachers' commitment to their work. Because validation and comprehensive instrument content were necessary, the re-

researcher sought knowledgeable people for comments and suggestions. The instrument used in the study was a validated questionnaire constructed by the researcher after reading articles and journals. It consisted of two parts. Part I dealt with the indicators of the sustainable development orientation regarding environmen-

tal awareness, knowledge economy, economic growth, and inclusive education. Part 2 dealt with the commitment to the work of teachers in terms of affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment. The following interpretations of the data are found below.

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Sustainable development adaptation is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Sustainable development adaptation is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Sustainable development adaptation is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Sustainable development adaptation is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Sustainable development adaptation is not manifested.

This study used a five-point Likert scale to describe the provisions relating to teachers’

commitment to their work.

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The commitment to the work of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.59	Extensive	The commitment to the work of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The commitment to the work of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The commitment to the work of teachers is rarely manifested.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher followed the following procedures in this study. Permission to conduct the study. On January 15, 2023, the graduate student received an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School for the approval of the division superintendent, a letter of permission for

the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the concerned gender, and a letter addressed to the District Supervisor requesting permission to conduct the study. Then, another letter was sent to the Public Schools District Supervisor and the School Heads to distribute the questionnaires to the respondents. Upon ap-

proval, the researcher personally administered and facilitated the questionnaire's administration and distribution from January 22 to 27, 2023. The questionnaire was retrieved immediately after the conduct, and the gathered data was scored, recorded, and classified with the statistician's guidance on February 12-17, 2023. The computation results were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted based on the purpose of the study.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. *Informed Consent.* The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study and given ample explanations so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was clear that the respondent's involvement in the study was voluntary. If they ever refused to participate, they were not forced to do so by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to study the factors that hinder/promote conversational skills concerning teachers' sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers. *Vulnerability of Research Participants.* The study's respondents are teachers, so they are not considered vulnerable since all of them are of legal age and were not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set

at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. *Privacy and Confidentiality.* This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the natural source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the participants' privacy, it was assured that the researcher could only access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the natural source of information. *Risk, Benefits, and Safety* - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the

information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study—anybody who fits the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher respected the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier and sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication concerning the research was done honestly and fairly. To safeguard the respondents' welfare, the researcher properly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study's results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that other factors like the conflict of interest did not influence the respondents' responses. The respondents could access the findings of the study and the school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success. The Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them

and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials, which were ample and available in the study and were done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by properly encoding the respondents' ratings during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used, and the null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 significance level. The data gathered was tallied and treated using statistical Mean. The weighted arithmetic mean applies to options of different weights (Calmorin, 1998). In this study, the statistical tool was used to measure the sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers. Pearson's r . The person product-moment of the correlation coefficient is a linear correlation to find the degree of the association of two sets of variables (Calmorin, 1998). In this study, this statistical tool was used to determine the significant relationship between sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers. Regression Analysis. The regression analysis was used to determine the domains of sustainable development adaptation that significantly influence teachers' commitment to their work.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: sustainable development adaptation and instructional competence.

3.1. Sustainable development Adaptation of teachers in terms of environmental awareness—Indicated in Table 1 is the extent of sustainable development adaptation among teachers in terms of environmental awareness. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: providing relevant lessons on environmental awareness (4.42), giving lessons that promote responsible environmental behavior (4.26), and promoting and understanding environmental concepts, conditions, and issues (4.24 are always manifested, thus, very extensive. Meanwhile, providing lessons that help prepare learners to deal with controversial environmental issues (4.18) and lessons that address all important components of environmental literacy (4.12) are often manifested, thus extensive. The overall mean rating of the extent of sustainable development adaptation of teachers in terms of environmental awareness is 4.24, or very extensive. This gives the impression that the extent of sustainable development adaptation of teachers in terms of environmental awareness is always manifested. This indicates that teachers are always adapting to sustainable development to enhance learners' awareness of caring for our environment.

Table 1. Extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers in Terms of Environmental Awareness

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Promote and understand environmental concepts, conditions, and issues.	4.24	Very Extensive
2	Give lessons that promote responsible environmental behavior.	4.26	Very Extensive
3	Provide lessons that address all important components of environmental literacy.	4.12	Extensive
4	Provide relevant lessons on environmental awareness.	4.42	Very Extensive
5	Provide lessons that help prepare learners to deal with controversial environmental issues.	4.18	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.24	Very Extensive

Zhang et al. (2021). When raising awareness about environmental issues, a good place to start is by including lessons about the environment in school curriculums. Teach children about reducing waste, reusing resources, and recycling materials. Organize tree-planting days at school and teach children that trees are important to the environment. Encourage children to switch off all appliances and lights when not in use. Also, encourage children to ensure taps are properly closed after use and to use water sparingly. Environmental awareness means being informed about our natural surroundings and understanding how our actions affect the well-being of our local and global environments. The environment refers to all parts of nature, living, and nonliving. Being aware of the environment is important because of the increasing environmental challenges the world is experiencing such as climate change, deforestation, droughts, floods, global warming, water scarcity, and pollution (Steffen et al., 2018). Education is recognized as a vital tool that not only imparts knowledge but also cultivates the values, perceptions, and awareness needed to tackle current environmental challenges. A major concern is the integration of sustainable development principles into educational curricula (Moustairas et al., 2022). Education is pivotal in advancing modern society's goal of achieving harmony between humans and nature.

3.2. *Competencies for the Knowledge Economy*—Meanwhile, Table 2 presents the

To properly prepare students for the demands of the future workforce, educators need to build a particular set of abilities in the ever-evolving knowledge economy. According to Schunk and Greene (2019), these capabilities include the capacity to develop critical thinking and problem-solving abilities and a thorough comprehension of the subject matter. The emphasis is on integrating technology into teach-

ing techniques since it enables teachers to engage students creatively and gives them the digital literacy needed in today's workforce. Like many frustrated commuters, urban planner and biking advocate Keisha Mayuga (2020) turned to cycling as an efficient way to navigate Metro Manila's traffic nightmare. However, it was not until the COVID-19 pandemic hit that mass public transport became a crisis extent of sustainable development adaptation among teachers in terms of competencies for the knowledge economy. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: I have my family and people around me to give comfort (4.38), inculcate the value of living a sustainable lifestyle to overcoming poverty (4.36), talking to co-workers about the challenges of working in a new arrangement in time of disaster helped me (4.30) and living in a modest life (4.21) are always manifested, thus, very extensive. Meanwhile, I get only accurate information regarding the disaster (4.10), which is oftentimes manifested thus extensively. The overall mean rating of competencies for the knowledge economy is 4.27, or very extensive. This means that teachers always manifest the extent of sustainable development adaptation. This indicates that teachers always show modesty and practice economy in their lifestyles. Zhao (2019) argues that helping teachers and students develop a growth mindset is important. To adjust to the ever-changing needs of the knowledge economy, a mindset focused on ongoing learning and improvement is essential. In addition to encouraging pupils to grow resilient and love learning, this calls on instructors to embrace new challenges and opportunities for professional development. Teachers can better prepare their pupils for success in a society that is becoming more complex and knowledge-intensive by helping them develop a growth mindset.

Table 2. The Extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers in Terms of Competencies for the Knowledge Economy

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Inculcate the value of living a sustainable lifestyle to overcoming poverty.	4.36	Very Extensive
2	Live in a modest life.	4.21	Very Extensive
3	Talking to co-workers about the challenges of working in a new arrangement in times of disaster helped me.	4.30	Very Extensive
4	I have my family and people around me to give me comfort.	4.38	Very Extensive
5	I get only accurate information regarding the disaster.	4.10	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.27	Very Extensive

that left many Filipinos stranded between work and home, spurring into action. Within twenty hours, Mayuga launched Life Cycles PH in March 2020. The donation drive supplied more than a thousand health workers and frontline with bicycles to help them with their daily commutes. Today, she works with the World Bank as a local urban planning consultant. She continues to advocate for improved mobility, public transport, and safer biking roads in Metro Manila.

3.3. *Social capital*—Moreover, Table 3 presents the extent of sustainable development adaptation of teachers in terms of social capital among teachers. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: assisting my colleagues

Social capital—the networks, relationships, and social interactions that promote community collaboration and support—is essential to creating a sustainable learning environment. According to Putnam (2019), robust social networks

having difficulty in complying with school requirements (4.46), exhibiting calm behavior when dealing with school issues (4.37), and modeling to my colleagues good work ethics (4.33) in its extent are always manifested; meanwhile, befriend the school community (4.19) and I maintain a good interpersonal relationship with my students, co-teachers, and stakeholders (4.15) extent is oftentimes manifested. The overall mean rating of social capital is 4.30 or very extensive. This means that the teachers oftentimes manifest the extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers. This indicates that the teachers always showed good work ethics in the school by providing a positive learning environment that is child-friendly.

in educational environments can foster professional learning communities, improve teacher cooperation, and create a feeling of shared purpose. To achieve long-term sustainability in education, schools must build social capital to

Table 3. Extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers in Terms of Human Social Capital

No	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Modeled to my colleague’s good work ethics.	4.33	Very Extensive
2	Befriend the school community.	4.19	Extensive
3	Assist my colleagues having difficulty in complying with school requirements.	4.46	Very Extensive
4	I maintain a good interpersonal relationship with my students, co-teachers, and stakeholders.	4.15	Extensive
5	Exhibit calm behavior when dealing with school issues.	4.37	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.30	Very Extensive

create a more unified and supportive atmosphere that supports the well-being of both teachers and students. Leithwood and Sun (2019) emphasize the importance of leadership in utilizing social and human capital. They contend that using social and human capital to propel academic advancements is a critical function of proficient school administrators. Encouraging a collaborative school culture and placing a high priority on teacher skill development can have a big influence on sustainability and educational performance. Their research highlights the significance of leadership in harmonizing resources and support systems with sustainable development objectives, which in turn improves the overall efficacy of the educational system. Tilbury (2019), there is a growing correlation between sustainability in education and the inclusion of social and environmental themes in the curriculum. She points out that integrating social responsibility and environmental stewardship topics into lesson plans promotes the development of human and social capital. Teachers help create a more sustainable future by em-

powering pupils to take on global concerns and instilling a sense of responsibility. Tilbury’s research demonstrates how education can trigger more significant societal changes, which is consistent with the ideas of sustainable development.

3.4. *The summary of the extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers*—Table 4 summarizes the Extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers in terms of its indicators: environmental awareness, competencies for the knowledge economy, and social capital among teachers. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: social capital (4.30), competencies for the knowledge economy (4.27), and environmental awareness (4.24) exhibit very extensive. The overall mean rating of 4.27 suggests that the teacher’s sustainable development adaptation is always manifested, thus very extensive among teachers. In sustainable development, social and human capital are vital in determining how well educational systems work and how well teachers perform.

Human capital, which includes people’s skills, knowledge, and capacities, is crucial for educators’ continuous professional development, claims Becker (2019). Teachers can improve their teaching methods and raise student learn-

ing results by investing in their human capital through ongoing professional development and training. In addition to helping individual educators.

Table 4. Summary on Extent of Sustainable Development Adaptation of Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Environmental awareness	4.24	Very Extensive
2	Competencies for the Knowledge Economy	4.27	Very Extensive
3	Social capital	4.30	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.27	Very Extensive

Education is a transformative force in sustainable development, driving change by deepening understanding of critical issues such as environmental challenges, social justice, and economic efficiency (Arabadzhyiev et al., 2020). Integrating these elements into educational frameworks prepares individuals to address complex global problems and contribute effectively to a more sustainable and equitable world. This approach ensures that education transcends mere information transfer, playing a vital role in cultivating informed and proactive citizens who can engage with and solve pressing sustainability issues. Tilbury (2019), there is a growing correlation between sustainability in education and the inclusion of social and environmental themes in the curriculum. She points out that integrating social responsibility and environmental stewardship topics into lesson plans promotes the development of human and social

capital. Teachers help create a more sustainable future by empowering pupils to take on global concerns and instilling a sense of responsibility. Tilbury’s research demonstrates how education can act as a trigger for more significance.

3.5. *Extent of Commitment to the Work of Teachers*—Indicated in Table 5 is the extent of Commitment to the Work of Teachers in terms of Affective commitment among teachers. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: confident that I can cope with major problems and crises (4.43), Demonstrate confidence in my ability to carry out a task or job (4.38), and believing that I can achieve whatever I set my mind to (4.34) are always manifested, thus very extensive, while self-assured in uncertain situations (4.21) is oftentimes manifested which means extensive.

The overall mean rating of affective commitment is 4.30, or very extensive. This means that teachers always manifest the extent of their commitment to work. This indicates that the teachers exhibit a very extensive commitment to work

and demonstrate excellent performance in dealing with the school’s disasters and crises. Affective commitment can be deeply understood as the emotional connection and sense of belonging a worker feels toward their organization.

Table 5. The Extent of Commitment to Work of Teachers in Terms of Affective Commitment

No.	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Demonstrate confidence in your ability to carry out a task or job.	4.38	Very Extensive
2	Confident that I can cope with major problems and crises.	4.43	Very Extensive
3	Believe that I can achieve whatever I set my mind to.	4.34	Very Extensive
4	Do not be easily deterred by difficulties or setbacks.	4.16	Extensive
5	Self-assured in uncertain situations.	4.21	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.30	Very Extensive

This commitment reflects a worker’s genuine affection for their workplace, manifesting in a profound emotional investment in their role and the organization’s mission. According to Amin et al. (2018), this emotional bond influences several critical aspects of organizational behavior. Workers who experience high levels of affective commitment are more likely to exhibit a strong desire to remain with the organization, driven by their love and attachment rather than external factors. Furthermore, affective commitment is associated with an individual’s emotional attachment and involvement in an organization, as stressed by Ardiansyah and Afandi (2019). Since it is what they genuinely want to do, those who are very committed to their work will persevere. They evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of quitting the organization based on what they believe they will lose. Those who stick around, because they are dedicated to being reliable, do so out of obligation rather than choice. Affective commitment significantly enhances employees’ work experience by fostering enthusiasm and a deep alignment with their

employer’s goals and objectives. According to Hashmi, Ahmad, and Nawaz (2021) and Ullah, Kamran, Akram, Nawaz, and Rehman (2021), when employees possess high affective commitment, they are more likely to approach their work with vigor and a sense of purpose, which in turn supports the overall success of the organization. This emotional attachment often translates into greater job satisfaction and a higher commitment to the organization. Continuance commitment Table 8 presents the extent of the Commitment to Work of Teachers in terms of continuance commitment among teachers. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: stay positive in the face of setbacks and failure (4.42), sort out difficulties and not let them affect other aspects of their work (4.36), believing things will always work out in the end (4.25) and concentrate on the positive side of the situations (4.22) are always manifested, thus, very extensive, while encouraging others to think positively (4.12) is often manifested, thus extensive.

Table 6. The Extent of Commitment to Work of Teachers in Terms of Continuance Commitment

No.	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Stay positive in the face of setbacks and failure.	4.42	Very Extensive
2	Believe things will always work out in the end.	4.25	Very Extensive
3	Concentrate on the positive side of the situation.	4.22	Very Extensive
4	Encourage others to think positively.	4.12	Extensive
5	Sort out difficulties and do not let them affect other aspects of their work.	4.36	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.27	Very Extensive

The overall mean rating of allocated resources is 4.27, or very extensive. This means that the teachers always manifest the extent of commitment to the work of teachers in terms of continuance commitment. This indicates that the schools are exhibiting very extensive commitment to work in the DepEd and deliver quality education. Continuance commitment refers to the obligation employees feel to stay with their organization due to their circumstances, particularly considering the financial and social consequences of leaving. According to Baoc-Daguisonan (2018), this type of commitment is driven by the perceived benefits of remaining with the organization compared to the potential drawbacks of departing. For educators, the decision to continue in their roles often hinges on assessing these costs and benefits, with the advantages of staying outweighing the disadvantages of leaving. This commitment ensures that teachers remain in their positions, motivated by the stability and benefits of their current employment. Kasogela (2019) suggests that a negative relationship exists between good work conduct and ongoing dedication. Job retention often

stems from employees' concerns about losing the benefits associated with their current position rather than from a deep-seated commitment to the organization. In some cases, employees choose to stay because they perceive that the costs of leaving would outweigh the benefits. This is particularly relevant in emerging nations, where an employee's commitment to their employer can be a strong indicator of their connection to the organization and reluctance to resign. Moreover, there has been inconsistent research on the impact of loyalty on an organization's performance. According to others, maintaining organizational commitment does not improve performance and makes employees more resistant to change (Chigeda et al., 2022). Others argue that specific circumstances determine the relationships between variables. Abdul Rashid's research suggests that an organization's steadfast dedication to success matters more in organizations with entrepreneurial cultures regarding Malaysian enterprises' financial performance and organizational culture. In these situations, employees are motivated to work harder and perform better for the organization to safeguard

their interests.

3.6. *Normative commitment*—Table 7 presents the extent of normative commitment among teachers to the work of teachers. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: commitment to work of teachers in terms of normative commitment (4.46), setting clear short- and long-term goals for myself frequently (4.37), and showing determination to achieve goals in demanding situations (4.36) are always manifested, thus very extensive; meanwhile, consistently strive to meet targets and objec-

tives (4.19) and having a strong sense of what I want to achieve from my job and career (4.12) are oftentimes manifested, thus extensive. The overall mean rating of normative commitment is 4.30, or very extensive. This means that teachers always manifest the extent of their commitment to their work in terms of normative commitment. This indicates that the teachers are exhibiting very extensive commitment to work by planning, implementing, and achieving the goals despite the challenges in demanding situations.

Table 7. The Extent of Commitment to Work of Teachers in Terms of Normative Commitment

No.	Survey Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Show determination to achieve goals in demanding situations.	4.36	Very Extensive
2	Set clear short- and long-term goals for myself frequently.	4.37	Very Extensive
3	Consistently strive to meet targets and objectives.	4.19	Extensive
4	Kept focused on the end goal at all times, regardless of setbacks.	4.46	Very Extensive
5	I have a strong sense of what I want to achieve in my job and career.	4.12	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.30	Very Extensive

Al Jabri and Ghazzawi (2019) describe normative commitment as an individual’s feeling of duty based on their perceived connection to the organization’s goals. Unlike affective commitment, characterized by a strong emotional attachment that drives individuals to stay with the organization, normative commitment is more about a sense of obligation. This obligation stems from the belief that remaining with the

organization is the right thing to do. In teaching, normative commitment reflects the degree to which educators feel it is morally correct or obligatory to remain at their institution. Normative commitment refers to a person’s perception of their duty to the organization based on moral principles, indicating that staying with the organization is the right thing to do. Individuals who exhibit strong normative commitment feel

a deep sense of obligation to continue their association with the organization they are part of. According to Allen and Meyer, as cited by Kalitanyi (2022), normative commitment reflects the belief that employees have a moral obligation to remain with their employer. Those with high normative commitment are motivated to stay with their organization because they consider it to be the ethically correct choice.

3.7. *Summary on Extent of Commitment to work of teachers*—Table 8 summarizes the

extent of teachers’ commitment to their work in terms of affective, continuance, and normative commitment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: affective commitment (4.30), continuance commitment (4.27), and normative commitment (4.27) are always manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.28 suggests that teacher commitment to work is always manifested, thus very extensive, among teachers.

Table 8. Summary on Extent of Commitment to Work of Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Affective commitment	4.30	Very Extensive
2	Continuance commitment	4.27	Very Extensive
3	Normative commitment	4.27	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.28	Very Extensive

Al-Jabari and Ghazzawi (2019) discovered in another study that affective commitment was a favorable opinion of the organization. Additionally, it was stated that a person’s ideals and attitude toward the organization are strongly correlated. It’s obvious how much someone enjoys and wants to be a group member when they join and begin to participate. According to Meyer and Allen’s model, several factors, such as the demands of the job, the organization’s role clarity, the goals themselves and the level of manageable difficulty in achieving them, peer cohesion, equity of opportunity, and compensation, perceived personal importance, and timely and constructive feedback, have a significant impact on affective commitment. Continuance commitment is influenced by two primary antecedents: the availability of alternatives and employee investments. Investment sources include the time, money, and effort employees have dedicated to their organization throughout their tenure. Employees with high continuance

commitment evaluate these investments when contemplating leaving their jobs, considering the value of their investments. This assessment creates a sense of obligation to stay, as they perceive that departing would mean losing the benefits of their accumulated efforts and resources (Oh Sawang, 2021). Normative commitment is an employee’s obligation to continue with an organization for moral or ethical reasons. According to Al-Belushi and Al-Harbi (2019), this type of commitment stems from a feeling that staying with the organization is the proper thing to do. Employees with a strong normative commitment frequently believe that leaving would violate their principles or breach their feelings of responsibility.

3.8. *A significant relationship between the extent of sustainable development adaptation and commitment to the work of teachers*—It can be depicted that Pearson’s correlation showed a significant correlation between the extent of sustainable development adaptation ($r=0.767$;

p<.001) and the commitment to the work of teachers in the Digos Oriental District. Table 11 revealed a significant relationship between the extent of sustainable development adapta-

tion and teachers' commitment to their work in Digos Oriental District. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis must be rejected for the results to suggest significant results.

Table 9. Significant Relationship Between Sustainable Development Adaptation and Commitment to Work of Teachers

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Implementation of CIP	0.767	<0.001	Significant	Reject H0

The study's finding is explained by Borrero (2018), who states that teachers today are so overwhelmed with the many tasks assigned to them that they already prioritize the issue of their sustainable development adaptation to which they are supposed to adhere. Teachers today have lost their passion for teaching meaningfully and care less about developing their students to acquire life-long learning skills. Moreover, Frankenberg, Taylor, and Merseeth (2019) conform with the findings of the study that teacher attrition is occurring at an alarming rate as a substantial number of teachers are leaving the teaching profession before retirement because they are underpaid, are afforded too few opportunities to improve their teaching skills,

have lack of support and are not adequately rewarded or recognized for their efforts. These teachers often limit their commitment and their engagement with the school as a means of survival, or they come to school unprepared for the lesson and unenthusiastic in delivering the lessons to the students.

3.9. *On the indicators of sustainable development adaptation that significantly influence the commitment to the work of teachers*—Table 10 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of sustainable development adaptation that significantly influence the commitment to work of teachers in Digos Oriental District.

All indicators of continuous improvement program provided, namely competencies for knowledge economy (0.152), human and social capital (0.115), and inclusive education (232), except environmental awareness (0.100) indicate statistically significant influence commitment to work of teachers in Digos Oriental District This gives empirical evidence to show that the indicators of sustainable development adaptation provided directly influences commitment to work of teachers. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.947 suggests that sustainable development adaptation accounts for 94.7In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with re-

gression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (106.420) and F-statistic are significant p<.001, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of commitment to the work of teachers. Thus, for sustainable development to be fully understood by many, particularly in basic education, the concept must be simplified so everyone can easily relate. Education is crucial in advancing society toward sustainable development by allowing individuals to apply their societal concepts in real-world settings. Its significance is shaped by both national policies and international efforts (Boevende Pauw, 2019). Maintaining high-quality edu-

Table 10. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Sustainable Development Adaptation Influencing Commitment to Work of Teachers

Model	Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t-value	p-value	Decision
Intercept (H)	4.356	0.066		61.083	<.001	
Intercept (H)	0.167	0.157		1.069	0.287	
Environmental awareness	0.203	0.073	0.100	2.119	0.041	Reject Null
Competencies for Knowledge Economy	0.132	0.092	0.158	1.444	0.152	Accept Null
Human and social capital	0.203	0.082	0.257	2.472	0.115	Accept Null
Inclusive education	0.097	0.083	0.221	0.949	0.232	Accept Null
R²	0.947					
F-value	106.420					
p-value	<.001					

cation is essential for upholding the principles of sustainable development. In addition, the curriculum today integrates sustainability in many aspects. Teachers are encouraged to create class activities that reflect students' development in valuing the environment while developing essential life skills necessary in work when they become adults. Education is recognized as a vital tool that imparts knowledge and cultivates the values, perceptions, and awareness needed to tackle current environmental challenges. A major concern is the integration of sustainable development principles into educational curricula (Moustairas et al., 2022). Education is pivotal in advancing modern society's goal of achieving harmony between humans and nature.

In other words, Schools today are very active in making the school turn into an environmental rehabilitation center. At a young age, students are educated to observe the basics of environmental conservation and protection. It does more than convey information; it also develops the values and skills essential for fostering environmentally conscious and socially responsible individuals. Within the framework of sustainable development, education serves as a driving force for change, enhancing understanding of environmental issues, social justice, and economic efficiency (Arabadzhyiev et al., 2020). To sum up, sustainable development adaptation contributes to teachers' commitment to their work in Digos Oriental District.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and implications drawn. Findings are based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions. The following are the study's findings, which are given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of sustainable development adaptation, in terms of its indicators, namely environmental awareness (4.24), competencies for the knowledge economy (4.27), and human and social capital (4.30), is very extensive in its practice. The overall

mean rating of 4.27 suggests that sustainable development adaptation is always manifested, thus very extensive, among the teachers in Digos Oriental District. The extent of the commitment to work in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment among schools in Digos Oriental District revealed that affective commitment (4.30), continuance commitment (4.27), and normative commitment exhibits always manifested, thus being very extensive. The overall mean rating of 4.28 suggests that a commitment to work is always manifested among the teachers in the Digos Oriental District. Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between the extent of sustainable development adaptation ($r=0.767$; $p<.001$) and commitment to work among teachers in the Digos Oriental District. All indicators of sustainable development adaptation provided, namely competencies for knowledge economy (0.152) and human and social capital ins (0.115), except environmental awareness (0.041), indicate a statistically significant commitment to the work of teachers in Digos Oriental District.

4.1. Conclusion—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions to wit; Digos Oriental District teachers extensively exhibited environmental awareness, competencies for the knowledge economy, and human and social capital in their practice of sustainable development adaptation. The extent of commitment to work in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment among teachers in Digos Oriental District revealed that affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment are extensive in their profession. There is a significant correlation between the extent of sustainable development adaptation and teachers' commitment to their work in the Digos Oriental District. Indicators of competencies in the knowledge economy and human and social capital indicate that they are statistically significant in influencing the commitment to the work of teachers in the Digos Oriental District.

4.2. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations to wit; Public School District Supervisors in Digos Oriental District may look to other factors that contribute to effective practices of sustainable development adaptation and integrate them into the curriculum to utilize and maximize resources to improve learning outcomes as policy inputs in the future. School Heads may sustain practices that strengthen teachers' sustainable development adaptation and continually improve learning outcomes, and they may encourage their respective schools to do the same and continuously improve themselves. Other factors that may influence teachers' commitment to curriculum and instruction may be explored, and the results may be considered. Future research may include the underlying empirical investigations on the process and mechanism of sustainable development adaptation to enhance their dedication and commitment towards their functions.

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